

Problems faced by teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economic disadvantaged regions and suggestions for solutions: A case study

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Abstract. The aim of this research was to reveal the problems experienced by teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economic disadvantaged regions, the main reasons of the problems and the solutions they found, and to present a case analysis with findings and suggestions. This research is expected to contribute greatly to the emergence of problems that are constantly seen, heard or never known, and to understand the problems and the students who experienced these problems. It was carried out in a state secondary school with a population of students and parents from a socio-economically disadvantaged region in Bolvadin district of Afyonkarahisar Province. The sampling of the research consisted of teachers from 5 different subjects. As a result of this research, it was found that socio-economic problems in schools in the region that were the subject of the research affected the school, student success, absenteeism and education life. It was seen that the problems were caused by various reasons, and it was stated that these reasons were also noteworthy. In terms of education, it was understood that it was difficult to find fast and permanent solutions that this process could be cooperative and only the effects of reducing the problems could be possible.

Keywords: Disadvantaged regions, secondary school, teachers

Introduction

One of the most important factors affecting the quality of education is the problems that educators, who have a curricular role for the development of societies, face while performing their profession. It is thought that the problems experienced by teachers constitute the basis of education problems in general (Uygun, 2012).

To take a look at the professional problems experienced by teachers, academic career barriers, additional course differences, different graduation areas, lack of support from school administrations, lack of counseling services in schools, not being appreciated by supervisors, work and private life circles, high scores and disadvantaged areas can be negative perception of the profession. Problems such as the difficulty of appointment due to regions, the problem of the employment of substitute teachers (Polat, 2014) who cannot be appointed can be given as examples suitable for this title.

Regions that can be considered disadvantaged offer less opportunities for people in terms of economic, sociological and cultural conditions and educational status. It is an accepted fact that education is very important in these regions and their surroundings. Social self-realization of the individual is possible through education. The disadvantage mentioned in this research is social and economic. OECD (2012) defines socioeconomic disadvantage as living in worse social and economic conditions and being in a lower status in society than other people in general. In other words, it emerges in a place where families

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struggle with economic problems, parents live apart in some cases, there are second marriages, broken family types and many psychological problems are experienced, a mass of uninterested parents, an out-of-centre or ignored region. It is also observed that such schools are addiction centers in some regions.

Recent researches have shown that teachers in schools facing difficult conditions need to work harder and be more dedicated than their peers in more favorable socioeconomic conditions. Furthermore, they must maintain this effort to sustain development, as success can be short-lived and fragile under difficult or challenging conditions (Whitty, 2001; Whitty and Mortimore, 1997). Especially in recent years, studies have been carried out on the effect of the general situation of disadvantaged regional schools on the school process and quality in disadvantaged regional secondary schools (Lupton, 2003), the problems faced by teachers working in socio-economically disadvantaged preschool institutions during the implementation of science activities (Önal, 2020) and social aspects. Studies dealing with issues such as the problems faced by social studies teachers working in disadvantaged areas (Taşdemir, 2016) have taken their place in the literature.

As seen in the studies done so far, teachers and students in those disadvantaged schools are often negatively affected. Thus, it is very important to examine the problems in these schools in detail, to understand to the main reasons of the problems, to try to reach solutions with education if any, or out of education, and to inform the relevant authorities about this issue.

The aim of this study was to understand and interpret the problems teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economically disadvantaged regions faced and their solutions to these problems, with the opinions of the teachers who experienced working in socio-economically disadvantaged regions.

Within the framework of the problem statement “What are the problems teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economically disadvantaged regions face and their solutions to these problems?” answers were sought to the following questions:

1. What kind of problems do teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economically disadvantaged regions face?
2. What are the main reasons for the problems faced by teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economically disadvantaged regions?
3. What do teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economically disadvantaged regions think about the impact of these situations on student achievement?
4. What kind of temporary solutions do teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economically disadvantaged regions produce within the school for the problems they face?
5. What do teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economically disadvantaged regions recommend for a permanent solution to the problems face?

Method and paradigm of research

The paradigm of this research is interpretive as it is ontologically and epistemologically based on subjective and inter-subjective views of the individuals based on their perspectives (Gunbayi & Sorm, 2020). Accordingly, a qualitative approach was chosen in this study. Because in the research, individual interviews with the participants was carried out and their views on the research topic were included and supported by documents. In this context, a descriptive case study with holistic single case design was used. Case studies are deep-based studies that try to richly describe events that occur in their natural conditions, under the constraints of time and space, using various data collection tools (Yin, 2017).

Sampling

Sampling was formed by selecting among different subject teachers working in Kemalettin Sami Pasa Secondary School in Bolvadin district of Afyonkarahisar, in accordance with the holistic single case design. The study group of this research was chosen on a voluntary basis. In this study, it was tried to understand the problems faced by the teachers working in the secondary school located in an economically and socially disadvantaged region in the Bolvadin district of Afyonkarahisar province and to examine the solutions they found with a case study. The sampling of the research consisted of 5 participants, one each from Science, Turkish, Social Studies, Mathematics and Religious Culture and Moral Science teachers working at Kemalettin Sami Pasa Secondary School. In the research, convenient sampling, which is one of the purposeful sampling techniques, was used, adding speed and practicality to research. Because in this method, the researchers chooses a situation that is close to them and easy to access (Palys, 2008). The sampling of the research were 5 subject teachers selected on voluntary basis. As seen in Table 1, the teachers participating in the research were in the subjects of science, Turkish, religious culture and moral science, mathematics, and social sciences. In terms of educational status, all of the teachers were under-graduate.

Table 1.

Distribution of participants according to subjects

Participants	Status	Subject	Graduation
P1	Teacher	Science	Undergraduate
P2	Teacher	Turkish	Undergraduate
P3	Teacher	Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge	Undergraduate
P4	Teacher	Maths	Undergraduate
P5	Teacher	Social Information	Undergraduate

Data collection

The data related to the research were collected from the teachers through interviews and documents between February 20th and March 20th, 2023. A recording device was used to record and keep data during the interview. Two different qualitative data collection methods were used in the study. The first of these data collection methods was interview forms. Individual interview forms based on open-ended questions and semi-structured interview questions were used to get the opinions of the participants on the problems they experienced. Interviews with the participants lasted approximately 30 minutes. In terms of efficiency and time saving, the interview was continued by recording on a voice recorder. The second data collection method in the research was the school documents of all kinds of correspondence, minutes and other documents that contained the success of the students, the student behavior and information such as absenteeism.

Ethical procedures

Scientific research ethics were followed at all stages of the research: (1) ethics committee approval of the research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 1 decision numbered 8 on 08 on January 10th, 2023 and (2) an informed consent form was signed by the participants prior to the interview.

Validity and reliability of the research

In order to increase the internal and external validity and reliability based on the criteria of credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability, (Lincoln and Guba, 1985) of the qualitative data, followings were carried out: (1) In order to increase the internal validity (credibility) of the research, in addition to interview, documents were also used in data collection and questions were created with the literature review, and immediately afterwards, preliminary interviews were held with the participants to

finalize the interview form. Then, semi-structured interview forms based on open-ended questions were created. (2) in order to increase the external validity (transferability) sampling was formed by selecting among different subject teachers via purposive sampling method based on voluntarism to get views of participants based on their perspectives, (3) in order to increase the internal reliability (confirmability) of the research following the coding by two independent researchers, Cohen's kappa coefficient was calculated to determine inter-rater reliability of themes as 0.83, a perfect level of agreement between the codings d) in order to increase the external reliability (dependability) of the research, all data collected were kept accessible on demand (Landis and Koach, 1977; Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Cohen, Mannion and Morrison, 2007, Gunbayi, 2018).

Data Analysis

In qualitative data analysis, the thematic and descriptive analysis (Cohen, Mannion & Morrison, 2007, Gunbayi, 2018) were used in the research to analyze the data obtained from interviews, and documents. First, the interview recordings were transcribed verbatim, then coded using the Atlas.ti qualitative software together with the data obtained from the documents. Finally, the codes and themes were arranged and the results were analyzed and interpreted.

Findings

1. The problems in secondary schools in socio-economic disadvantaged regions

In the first sub-problem of the problems in secondary schools in socio-economic disadvantaged regions were asked to the participants. The opinions of teachers working in socio-economically disadvantaged secondary schools about the problems they faced and the themes related to those problems are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The theme and sub-themes of the problems faced by teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economic disadvantaged regions

As seen in Figure 1, the problems faced by teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economic disadvantaged regions gathered under the sub-themes of negative perception towards the profession, teachers' housing problem, failure of students to do their homework, low student achievement, special needs student issues, absenteeism problems, attending unprepared for class, crowded classrooms,

students' distraction and reluctance towards lessons, foreign students and cultural problems, lack of staff at school, low class attendance and teachers' transportation problem.

First of all, the interviewees were asked about the definition of "socio-economically disadvantaged region" and all of the participants touched on the negative concepts of "deficiency, weakness, differences, bad situations" with an almost similar statements.

Here come the differences between students. In these differences, especially the social order and the differences in literacy rates at work, the inadequacy in the income level can spread to the education level of the parents (P5).

I think of regions where children's economic conditions are poor. I especially think of places where their families had low levels of education (P4).

When it comes to disadvantaged regions, of course, the economic situation of the family is weak or moderate, and this is reflected in school and education (P2).

Socially and economically substandard region (P3).

It is a concept that includes social and economic factors such as income, economic situations as well as culture and education. We can say that there is a lack of these (P1).

Participants were asked if their opinion on whether the school they worked for was in a disadvantaged area, and four people said they were in exactly that area:

Yes, I think so. Although the school I work at is in the district center, it is a school on the coast we call more provincial. Although the family ties in this region seem to be very strong with each other, unfortunately this is not the case in terms of education. More children aspire to do the jobs they see in the family, they have little to do with the future that education will bring. They see education as an advantage only to get a diploma (P5).

Yes, I think so. Especially in terms of parents, we are in a disadvantaged school due to the low level of education of our parents, that is, graduates from high school equivalent schools, graduates from primary school equivalent schools. We are in a socio-economically disadvantaged region. Because we live in a region where there are very few social, cultural activities. Since our school is in that kind of area in particular, we live in this economically dead zone. We suffer from family members who have experienced separation and troubled families. In addition, the fact that family members have communication problems with each other reflects negatively on children (P4).

Well, our school looks like the central school, but because the economic situation is also bad, because this is a transition zone to the village, and because there are usually workers' children, so economically it is bad. I think it is a disadvantaged school, we are experiencing this and we have been living it for 5 years. So I think that's the case (P2)

I think that the school I work for is in a disadvantageous area in terms of all factors. Because I think it is in a disadvantageous region like the 3rd degree in terms of income, education and culture. In addition, I see it as a school that includes disadvantaged students in terms of the students covered by our school. Because it accommodates students with cognitive autism or IEP. The way families approach school and the educational status of families are generally low. The vast majority of families are minimum wage earners. She can't take care of her children enough. But I think that socio-economic factors such as population, transportation, health, labor force, agriculture, tourism, justice and culture constitute a problem for our school and our region, and that they are in a disadvantaged area. In addition, another factor that reinforces the fact that our school is a disadvantaged regional school is that it also hosts foreign students such as Syrians (P1).

One participant stated that the school was "partially" in a disadvantaged area:

In part, many of the students' families are substandard in economic terms, so they don't have enough reference books. In addition, although their families want to help because their education level is at the primary school level, they may be inadequate in this regard (P3).

After the definitional questions of the interview, the problems faced by teachers working in socio-economically disadvantaged secondary schools were asked to the participants with some sub-questions.

The four participants agreed that the students should come to the lessons prepared, mentioning that the lessons were generally unprepared and that there were not many students who came prepared.

Students don't come to class very prepared. Both as a brain and as a mental structure, I think they still see themselves at the elementary school level, even though they are in middle school. Parents are also not aware of this future and the LGS (Upper Secondary School Entrance Exam) exam that we will take in the eighth grade. We face unplanned work. Students don't have a goal they set for themselves. Because they don't have goals, they can't adapt to planned work; parents are not aware of this, or they approach some subjects with prejudice, or they approach them in a completely simple way and say, "Normal, okay, we do, we pass. Isn't it physical education, music, painting?" They see some main subjects as very difficult and say "We will not be able to do these things anyway" and give up like this (P5).

Unfortunately, students do not come to the classes prepared. Especially we have a shortage of books and notebooks. So we normally text families, we call them, we tell them at parent meetings, but we even tell the children that they should check in the evening. They do not check from the evening. Especially if we get up late in the morning, that is, if our school starts at half past eight, for example, they get up at eight and immediately pack their bags in such a hurry and bring their bags like that, and there are no books, there are no notebooks, sometimes they do not bring homework, sometimes they do not bring the tests we give, sometimes there is a news from the topics we write. Especially today, for example, I experienced such an incident. The notebooks of the absent students were empty in large quantities. Parents do not pay attention to these (P4).

These are situations where students don't do homework, you know, "somehow my father works at home, he doesn't question. My mom is busy with other things," and they're unprepared. We've all been kids. There are too many situations where he is dealing with other things and not fulfilling his responsibilities (P2).

In general, our students do not come prepared for class. In classes of 15-20 people, 2 or at most 3 people come prepared. 7 and 8. The number of students who come prepared in the classes is 1 or maximum 2 people (P1).

In their opinions on the participation status of the course, three participants thought that the participation was low and two people had different opinions:

It's always limited to certain students. You know, there are students that we can add later, but active students are limited to certain people (P5).

Participation in the course can actually change as the year goes by. As the year goes by, as the kids get smaller, it's very different, especially between what we graduate from the eighth grade and the five that just arrive. Especially as I said, we have trouble doing homework, we have trouble raising fingers, or the child does not know the subject. For example, we have a lot of trouble because we do not know the subject. Especially in my major, because it's not very interesting, the topics don't participate so much because the kids have prejudices. Especially in elementary school, they are not very interested, so they can come to my class and middle school unprepared. My major is mathematics, by the way. Since there is a prejudice in mathematics, there is also a

prejudice in parents. Since there is prejudice in children, unfortunately, we may have problems in the participation of children in the course (P4).

Attendance at classes is limited to certain students. Participation is low in general terms (P2).

Two participants, unlike the other participants, expressed their opinions and stated that they had full participation in the course:

In my class, I see that all students are participating. (P1)

Although the level of participation in the course is good, the level of answering in terms of quality is insufficient. (P3)

When asked if they had faced undesirable student behavior in the course, two participants mentioned that they had behavior problems. One participant did not respond.

Yes, we do. There are students who cause problems. Especially students with individual needs, special needs (P5).

If the reflection on the school is that of course this is a financial problem, of course, we lived in time. In such houses, some discipline problems also occur in the family. This is reflected in the school by the student and he becomes a little more aggressive in his behavior (P2).

Two of the participants mentioned that there were no major problems:

Sometimes it happens, but it's not a huge problem. For example, some students want to stand and walk around when they should be sitting during class. Some of them disturb their friends on their left and right next to them. In these cases, it can be difficult to control the class. There's a lot of talk in class (P4).

There are no bullying students in our school that I have seen. Generally respectful. There are no students in our school who cause excessive problems. There are one or two students who are older in age. Sometimes they act irresponsibly with the psychology of adolescence (P1).

When asked whether there were students who were absent from school courses and supportive training courses, the participants mentioned that there was a problem of absenteeism, especially in foreign students, while in Turkish students, excuses were arbitrarily made, continuous reports were received and absences caused by transportation problems. Four participants expressed close statements on these issues:

Yes, there is. Especially in our foreign students, we experience the problem of absenteeism a lot, or in seasonal periods, as I said, there are times when we call it field, animal, workers, hoe time. Students are absent a lot during these periods or in special cases, we have students who go out of town by saying "we have a wedding" and "I don't know what I know, I have circumcision, I am going to my aunt, I am going to my sister", we have students who go away with illness. We live this from time to time. When we look at, we see that students cannot continue too much because of the service problem again, and they turn to central or different departments. But not all students are financially well. That's why there are students who attend the Support and Training Courses at the school. But these students are also limited.(P5).

We have students who are absent. Especially in foreign students, we had problems last year. This year, we have a general absenteeism problem in our students again. Especially since this is a cold country, we have a lot of students who have a lot of flu, who have a cold, who have a low immune system. That's why we are experiencing absenteeism this year as well. They can't come because of the shuttle situation and the distance of the school from the houses, and the service is as follows: we have a single service problem for those who will leave in the morning and take the new ones in the evening, for example this year. Last year we did not have such a problem, but this year our

students have to come by shuttle because the houses are far away. We don't have any students from the immediate vicinity. That's why they have trouble, of course they can have trouble staying in courses or coming to school.(P4).

If we are realistic, we expect them to attend the courses fully because they do not have extras such as private lessons. You know, it happens in certain places, that is, partly because our school is moving from the neighborhood. You know, coming and going at the time of the course is actually a material, materiality. You know, if it's a service, it's economical. If there was a school in the middle of the neighborhood, everyone would come for sure. You know, I also taught in the village. There is full participation in the courses we have in the village. The student has no choice but to be the teacher. In other words, he or she could have as much of a dream as the teacher in the village, as much as the teacher in the village taught, and he or she could have as much goal and success as the teacher in the village. So they were fully participating. There is a bit of a transportation problem here, again a material comes into play. Because of this, there is a situation of not coming to the course. But in such places, if the school is close to the houses, if it is in the middle of the neighborhood, the participation in the courses is much higher than in successful places. Because in successful places, there is much less participation in the courses because they spend their course time with private lessons and private education institutions. I can easily say this as I have worked in central places in the past years. (P2)

Families who have difficulty in meeting the service fee cannot send their children to courses (P3)

A participant's statement on this subject is given below.

I think courses are beneficial to eager students, and I see their success growing (P1)

2. The main reasons of the problems in secondary schools in socio-economic disadvantaged regions

In the second sub-problem of the views of teachers working in socio-economically disadvantaged secondary schools about the main reasons of the problems they experienced and the themes related to the root causes of the problems are given in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Themes on the main reasons of the problems faced by teachers in socio-economically disadvantaged secondary schools

As seen in Figure 1, the main reasons the problems faced by teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economic disadvantaged regions gathered under the sub-themes of low education level of

families, lack of additional resources and materials, students' transportation problems to school, counseling teacher need, indifferent attitude of the family, psychological problems, the location of school and negative reputation, cultural issues, impact of the environment and environmental problems, economic problems, seasonal worker status, fragmented family structure, social problems, family problems, working with unplanned, aimless and wrong methods and lack of a proper canteen.

When asked whether they thought the problems were caused by the student or the region where they lived, three of the participants mentioned the situation of the region in general, the situation of the students, and the impact of economic and social problems. One participant answered this question broadly along with the next question:

Yes, I do, and unfortunately I am experiencing this obviously. Especially the children of broken families are around us a lot, or we have parents of students who are having their second and third marriage. At a young age, our student parents were married or married. Therefore, unconscious parents are raising children who are not conscious, and unfortunately, their level of consciousness has not yet been fully fulfilled despite being parents. In addition, they have experienced and are experiencing differences in morality, respect and culture. We also have parents who have a culture conflict. The parents who lived in this area grew up in this region but married someone from a different region or married someone from a different country. That's why the child is trying to grow up in a culture conflict. Unfortunately, we see the difficulties of this in our lives. (P5)

I think it's because of both. I think it is especially due to the apathy of the parents. The students are trying to behave accordingly, so of course the parents behave. In other words, I can say that what they see in the family is actually imitating them at school. If children, for example, parents live at home, children experience the same things at school with their friends. (P4)

I can say that the problems I face as a teacher, the problems related to the psychosocial development of my students, the interest status of the families, income and culture differences. The number of parents who come to the school to follow their students is almost non-existent. But it comes if the teacher calls. Some students have difficulty accessing recommended resources (not resources related to my school). For example, if parents have the power to buy play dough, I will have students make "organelles of the cell" (P1).

The answer that differed between the answers to this question is the following statement of the participant, who saw the source of the problems as purely the student:

I think it's entirely due to the student; If they want to be a successful student, they can solve many problems. Rotating resources, such as exchanging books... (P3)

Economic problems, family problems, which were especially mentioned by the three participants who expressed their opinions on the impact of family problems and financial impossibilities on students, were the difficulty of students who could not meet even their basic needs to give themselves to classes, not to show behavioral problems and to adapt to school:

Yes, unfortunately it reasons problems. The economic situation is especially low, whether it is at a medium level or below average, of course, it also affects students. Because most of the parents who live here, most of the parents in our school, generally work for military wages or the two have to work together, the parents have to work. Therefore, it also affects the student (P4).

Family problems often affect students negatively. The child becomes more silent. It inhibits learning on its own. The financial situation, that is, the income, has some effect on the students. That is, when I give period projects, I choose projects accordingly since the family's financial situation is low (P1).

So we've seen the training for this as Maslow's "Hierarchy of Needs" really comes into play here. Because when the child comes to school, if he or she does not have a basic breakfast, his or her economic situation is not so encouraging, that is, when there are students who come before he or she can fully prepare his or her dress, how it is that education is on the top of the respect step. You know, we are in the part of the students who come without being able to meet the security, physiological needs in the family or something. Socio-economically disadvantaged places are at the first and second level of the hierarchy of needs. Obviously, we are trying to take them from there and take them to the upper rungs with the support of the teachers or the school administration, to cooperate with the family and to save them from there. Because when the kid is there, there are things like you said. So the parents are separated; I also went through the economic dimension of it, if the spiritual dimension was very, very tight. You know, both financially and spiritually, since ninety percent of the students are still in the first and second level, why didn't you study for them? Rather than why he doesn't fulfill his responsibilities, yes, we say that sometimes, we forget because they went through it. But you know, we catch the students who are here and have a little bit of light in their eyes and look at what we have been able to save as snow. Obviously, the expectation of other places from here is: once there are one or two Science High Schools from here, it is considered a success. Because the person who comes is already certain, it is known in the society that you are in a school that is disadvantaged. Therefore, it is even a profit for us to remove one or two students from among them. But actually, of course, it is necessary to equalize these things, at least to minimize them, and to save many children. Of course, this does not only mean to bring Science High School, it is to bring it to life. Because of the exam race, we are trying to bring to the forefront those who shine a little bit there. But here, students who are experiencing economic difficulties, who are experiencing spiritual problems, are a little further behind, and since they are also behind in exams, it is as if there is a lot of loss of education in such schools as children who are completely in the background. We are trying to save as much as we can, but unfortunately it is not happening. (P2)

Participants were asked whether there were socio-economic or cultural differences among the students and whether these differences were the source of the problems. Two participants stated that there were generally economic, social and cultural differences and that they negatively affected the psychology and mood of the student:

Yes, such differences exist because our students sometimes think that they are dressed as a beautiful brand and have the potential to show off to other students like this. Or the other student can emulate his clothes and save money in different ways, "Let me go to work, save money, and I can buy a branded shoe, a branded phone. In other words, instead of this, he can say "let me target this school" and he can make savings in different subjects. You know, there is the potential to save more days and follow the material popular culture in our students, not the accumulation of knowledge. There are also cultural differences between families. Especially since the region we live in is on the edge of the district, we see the great differences between a family living in the center and a family living in the region where our school is located. We have cultural differences among students. Yes, as I said, what I call broken family children are the children of parents who have married for the second time and are trying to grow up with a different culture. When he goes and meets mom or dad occasionally during the summer holidays, he comes up with a different culture on his return. This can lead to the breakdown of previous friendships and the exclusion of the student. Foreign students also have a difference. The fact that our foreign students cannot fully adapt to our culture from time to time and the cultural difference experienced by these students attract the attention of other students. These differences can sometimes isolate them at school school. They can be alone due to cultural differences, or if they are related to each other, they can unite and become a group ((P5).

Yes, there is. There are those who are above the intermediate level, there are those who are at the intermediate level, there are those who are below the middle. Of course, children are not

aware of this. In other words, our students, who are above the middle level, that is, in the part that we can call rich, can bully and make fun of the students who are at a low level, that is, economically low. Of course, children are not aware of this, but because there are such problems in families and in the part we call the environment, children can easily come and make fun of their friends who are in a bad economic situation. It happens in the classroom, it happens in the school. Because children are not aware of them. His mother and father are separated or his parents are united, so he can talk easily because he is not aware of the events. Actually, our children are not in the way that I am thirsty, I don't make fun of, I don't bully; Usually children who can talk about everything comfortably. That's why they talk about what happens at home, for example, in class, and they tell their friends. Kids who can tell everything, anywhere. For this reason, even when you buy something from the canteen in the friend environment, for example, there are many examples like "your mother is your father" or "your financial situation". They can make fun of those students or oppress them. To put it crudely, they can "crush", that is, their children (P4).

One participant also mentioned that there are differences especially in social, psychological and cultural terms:

There are differences between students socially, in terms of student personality and psychosocial. We have a student with autism spectrum disorder. We have four or five students with IEPs. We have foreign national, Syrian students. I think this leads to a difference and problems with other students (P1).

Participants were asked whether the fact that the school was in a socio-economically disadvantaged area had a negative impact on the reputation of the school and teachers. The three interviewees stated that the school was or was seen as socio-economically or locationally disadvantaged and therefore the parents who would send their children to this school avoided sending students to such schools, prejudiced and created an image that lowered the reputation of the school / teacher:

In today's world, where the school has a label in the school the student attends, such an approach comes to the fore when the student says "I go to this school", the school's success at work label or other activities. The activities of teachers come to the fore. Parents also direct their children according to this name of the schools. They may have negative thoughts about the school, the environment and the region (P5).

As an environment, I can say that unfortunately our school is in a slightly shallow area around us, so it is in a separate area from the district in terms of location. So we can have a shortage of stray dogs, there can be a shortage of animals at work environmentally, there can be animal attacks. It has happened to a lot of children in recent years. Kids can come by bike, they can come by electric motorcycle or motor, or they can come by electric bike. Therefore, environmental factors affect children in this way. Parents also fail in this place, drawing the image of a school outside the district and underestimating or seeing the group of students coming to the school (P4).

This is not only our district in general, but also in general districts, such schools are already known by name. You know, it's seen as a village school, or a little bit more out-of-center schools, it's seen in the countryside. So it's very big, yes, success is not expected, but for students who are at the bottom of big failures or students who have low nets, they say, "Why are these things low?" But before that, they don't say, "What can we do?" It's only when the problem is, "Why did they do it so low?" This is also our disadvantage. So I think everyone is aware of this (P2).

3. The impact of student problems on student success

In the third sub-problem of the opinions of the teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economically disadvantaged regions on the impact of these situations on student achievement are given below.

When asked about the status of students' participation in the supportive training courses and whether their experiences had an impact on their participation, four participants mentioned that the effect was social and economic, that the parents had difficulty in terms of transportation, that is, in meeting the service fee, and that the school was far away, that parents could not send the students due to cold weather conditions, so the participation was low and negatively affected. Of course, it was worth adding the reluctance of students and the apathy of the parents.

When we look at, we see that students cannot continue too much because of the service problem again, and they turn to central or different departments. But not all students are financially well. That's why there are students who attend the Support and Training Courses at the school. But these students are also limited ((P5).

They can't come because of the shuttle situation and the distance of the school from the houses, the shuttle goes like this; For example, we have a single service problem for those who will leave in the morning and buy new ones in the evening. Last year we did not have such a problem, but this year our students have to come by shuttle because the houses are far away. We don't have any students from the immediate vicinity. That's why they have trouble, they can have trouble staying in courses or coming to school, of course (P4).

If we are realistic, we expect them to attend the courses fully because they do not have extras such as private lessons. You know, it happens in certain places, that is, partly because our school is moving from the neighborhood. You know, coming and going at the time of the course is actually a material, materiality. You know, if it's a service, it's economical. If there was a school in the middle of the neighborhood, everyone would come for sure. You know, I also taught in the village. There is full participation in the courses we have in the village. The student has no choice but to be the teacher. In other words, he could have as much of a dream as the teacher in the village, as much as the teacher in the village taught, and he could have as much goal and success as the teacher in the village. So they were fully participating. There is a bit of a transportation problem here, again a material comes into play. Because of this, there is a situation of not coming to the course. But in such places, if the school is close to the houses, if it is in the middle of the neighborhood, the participation in the courses is much higher than in successful places. Because in successful places, there is much less participation in the courses because they spend their course time with private lessons and dershanes. I can easily say this because I have worked in central places in the past years. (P2)

Families who have difficulty in meeting the service fee due to financial insufficiency cannot send their children to courses. (P3)

One participant also commented below:

I think courses are beneficial to eager students, and I see their success increasing. (P1)

When asked about the students' distractions, reluctance to attend the course and the effect of their socio-economic status on their success or psychological status, all participants stated that economic, social, cultural and environmental problems negatively affected the students and their learning life. Family problems and indifferent attitudes of parents were also expressed as the biggest factor:

Yes, students are sometimes in the classroom within the school, but they are not there in spirit. When we look at him in the eye, he seems to be answering, as if he understands us, but after five minutes we realize that when we solve any question, the student does not fully understand and is out of the environment. He may be distracted, or he may have a different behavior disorder

in his mind, or he may not be able to get out of an event he is affected by, or he may continue to experience family problems at school, which is very normal for his age. Because our children are students who are in their teens, in the period of forming thoughts and ideas. He always has such a confusion in his mind, a reasoning, he does not know what to do or what to do. It decides which behavior is right wrong, good or bad more by looking at the teachers. Because the best idol for them is teachers. Of course this is true. Not wrong. But in addition to this, people who can be different idols, who can set goals at work, who can say "let me learn and envy the achievements of this". When I think about it, writers, poets, scientists from the environment or other provinces should know various professional groups or when they are not, our students should be able to reach such places by making sightseeing observations, they can visit museums and scientific travel places. I think this is a reason that will positively affect the success of our students (P5).

Let me put it this way, for example, we have children who can't buy shoes, or we have children who can't buy clothes. We warn children that there should be only one outfit in our school, for example. Because if we think that children all come with different clothes, for example, children can be the subject of making fun of each other, we can experience distress. That's why we usually want children to wear one outfit. In the situation reflected in the children, the reason why they are pensive at work is usually because they cannot buy shoes or, for example, we want something to be bought, they tell their father, but the parent responds negatively. Perhaps because of the financial situation. The child can think about this and wander in the lessons. For example, our big parents are too many. Our elderly parents are in our schools too much. The multitude of elderly parents also have such older children. Let me tell you about a problem we had recently: the child had trouble sleeping. I looked at the class and said, "What is happening to my child?" and so on, and then there was the girl. I said, "What's going on?" I said, "Do you have a problem?" He said, "No, sir." Then I asked again in between classes. "My teacher is not with my family, my mother is not with me," he said. Her sister was going to give birth and went to her. So we have a lot of troubles like this. Her sister is getting older, she's going to give birth, she's going to get married. If we look at the previous issues, they are absenteeism, for example. They say, "My sister and brother have a wedding, I attended it," and these students are affected in terms of their classes and achievements. When the parent is busy with the wedding and association affairs of their older children, the parental apathy reflects negatively on the child (P4).

As I said, if there is a problem at home or we don't know what to know, we have said one book, a student may be stuck on something very small. At recess, his friend may have picked something up in the canteen and even if he didn't, he might have hung out. You know, normal life is so fast and protracted that we can't see such a small trauma of children. He took a friend at recess, he didn't order him, he didn't eat it, he couldn't drink it, he said the book, he didn't get it, it was called trial money, it couldn't be given. Problems such as those who are attached to other problems in the house, such as your parents are separated and you went to your father, you couldn't go... And I hear that I did a study called the "room of secrets" for my own class, and that kind of thing was coming up there. When you open the student's insides, there are bad bad scenarios, very bad dramas. That's why they get distracted, they break away from the lessons a little bit, and so on. Of course, if everything is very good at home, if everything is taken away, if the socio-economic situation is good, the only concern of the student is "What does the teacher say?, What is being done here? How can I listen to the lecture?, How can I be successful?", but of course this happens a lot in schools like ours (P2).

Unfortunately, these situations of the students (living in socio-economically disadvantaged regions and their problems) have an impact on student success (P3).

I think that the most important factors affecting student success in our school are the lack of interest of families (social), the fact that there are generally low-income families (economic),

the effect of psychosocial learning situations (students with autism spectrum disorders, the adaptation of IEP and foreign students). I also observe that these situations adversely affect education and training at some points (P1).

In the 2022-2023 academic year, participants were asked about their students' LGS (Upper Secondary School Entrance Exam) results and how they evaluated their success status, their thoughts on success or failure, and the factors that may affect success / failure. Three of the participants mentioned that what the working students achieved could be a success in that respect, but there were also students who failed, that is, who did not work, who did not work planned, who did not show interest, who had small dreams or who had no dreams at all. The factors were expressed as the environment lived, parent apathy, economic, social, environmental and cultural problems:

When we look at last year's exam results, I see that our students are a few students who set realistic goals and they really reach their goals. I know that students are settled as science high schools, high schools with points, open high schools and vocational high schools. We observe that there is more placement with school points. Because the student is already focusing on his diplomat, as I said, with small goals, he is turning to some occupational groups that we call small tradesmen or trade or butchery at work (P5).

On LGS, there were two Science High Schools in LGS last year, there were three or four social sciences high schools, and we also had students who went to vocational high school, went straight to high school and openly studied high school. That was the case last year. We had a successful student, but we also had a failed student. We had more students going with school points, though. Failure starts from the child himself. More precisely, it starts in the family and ends in the child. Unfortunately, as I said, the fact that the child's parent is not interested in the child simply does not check books and books shows that the child does not have any labor on him. So when we give him homework, he doesn't follow his homework. We give it a week, we say it again when we check in next week, we say "bring it back next week". For example, we have parents who don't even do that. They are also very much influenced by the environment. For example, we have a problem in this environment. Obviously, we are in a region where mothers have the potential to travel a lot. You know, there is a lot of going to the day here, there is a lot of going to the evening outings. Last year, for example, I had one student who failed just because of that. For example, I have a student who has failed to take his mother for sightseeing, for evening outings, to take her here and there during the day. He couldn't do his homework, he couldn't focus on his studies (P4).

When I think in terms of the eighth grade central exam, the number of students is not 50-60 students because of our criticism just now, but we had 23 students, two subjects. Of these, even the central schools are doing this, our ten students can win, certain people can win. In our country, 4 5 students had the potential to win the central high schools. Two of them won science high school. Both three of them are close to the levels they can win, in fact, they got the points that could enter Science High School in other districts. In other words, our struggle with the teachers took place again in the center of the students, without missing the book, without missing their studies, and we put them into the exams. In fact, we seem to have centered and balanced the socio-economic level there a little bit. Of course, we had some benefit because the economic situation of those students and families was one click above the general one. But of course, 23 people and 10 people could have won the Science High School. There are dimensions to this that come from the very fifth grade. Since we live here in such a region, there have been any casualties in between. So, we were able to send two Science High Schools, which is a success for us. You know, as I said before, if two science high schools come from such a place, it is considered a success. Therefore, we can say that it is successful (P2).

One participant clearly mentioned only success:

I think our school was successful in terms of last year's LGS exam (P1).

When asked how the attitudes of the parents of the students on student success/failure and the parent profile were in terms of the region, they expressed their views as follows:

When we look at the student, the parent's mirror. The parent profile is usually in a situation where we can say primary, secondary or high school graduates, and almost no university graduates. This means that we see that they raise students who will live their own lives. We have a group of parents who don't have a very high level of awareness, or who don't know how to do it when they do. He thinks it's all about "study, study, study, don't get up from the book for 10 hours," but that's not it. The student can and should experience situations such as working for an hour or two to study efficiently, to evaluate the time well, to accelerate his reading. Unfortunately, the parents of our students visit the school from meeting to meeting, or because there is a major discipline problem and they do not come very close to the school until the class teacher calls them. Because he thinks, "I entrusted it to the school, I'm leaving." You know, that's a wrong idea. It should deal with the student one-on-one. It's true that he shouldn't come and go to school every day. However, both the student, the teacher and the administration should be aware that they are interested, and the student should feel this (P5).

When I give the homework to the children in the evening, they don't check their homework, they don't check their notebook books so that they can bring it full the next day. They do not care about the achievement evaluation exams, they do not care about the written statements, they do not care about the oral notes given, that is, the behavioral grades. Therefore, they do not come to the parents' meetings of the children. Children's success also seems to be insignificant. You know, the child leads to failure by thinking "my family is not behind me either" (P4).

There are cases where the parent profile, usually the worker, the working child, the mother also works. Parents' separate situations are not uncommon in such familial fissures. I know it because I've been here for five years from the old classes that I heard in the classes. In material terms, I can say that they are at the intermediate level or below the middle. We can see this from the fact that he already takes his clothing from his clothing during the year. In general, Ağılönü is called "butcher children, butchers". He has a bias anyway. You know, this is reflected in such behaviors and styles, etc., which is received negatively by others, but I can say that the economic situation of the family is middle and below. I can say that there is little interest in children for this school. So if we support it, if we force it, they can only come to the school and get into this communication. This is the case. You know, there are already situations such as "we are going to work, we can't come" and so on with the excuse of general school parent association meetings and parent meetings (P2).

The way families approach school and the educational status of families are generally low. The vast majority of families are minimum wage earners. She can't take care of her children enough. The parent profile is of little interest to our school, to speak. They are not relevant enough. Concerned parents are parents who are concerned with their student, who visit the school frequently, monitor their student and follow up on his condition. Their students usually succeed or solve many of their problems (P1)

4. Temporary suggestions to problems

In the fourth sub-problem of the opinions of teachers working in socio-economically disadvantaged secondary schools on temporary solutions to the problems they experienced are given below.

In the answers given to the interviewers about the counseling services in the school and how the problematic students were approached, what kind of temporary measures were taken, they stated that there was no counseling teacher in the school, that when a problem occurred in the school or in the classroom because they were not experts in counseling services, the teachers were in a difficult situation,

they took temporary measures, and in case of major problems, the counseling teacher came from the district only to deal with whatever the event was.

Our counseling teacher is not available at our school. He used to come once a week as an assignment, but now there is no counseling teacher who comes to our school regularly. Since there are many problems that students live with, teachers experience, and because of the disconnect, I think that there should be a counseling teacher in our school. When we meet such students, we have solutions in the form of written, verbal warnings, advices, suggestions or directions. This is how we approach both students and parents. We try to provide preventive counseling. Maybe as class counselors, but because there is no counseling teacher in our school, we may not be able to fully realize this. Because we are not experts. ((P5).

Unfortunately, we do not have a counseling teacher, there was an assignment last year, but this year there is none. He was a teacher who could come once a week, who could come in between, I would say he was a teacher who had a problem, who could come for the student, or where the student went to the teacher. The lack of a counseling teacher also affects us in our approach to children. Since I'm not usually an expert on this subject, I honestly don't want to ask too many questions when kids have problems, I can't get close, I have a fear of doing something wrong. I don't really want to ask questions because I'm not an expert. I don't want to overwhelm him, I don't want to make a wrong behavior and harass the child, or because I don't want to cause something wrong, I usually forward the students who have problems and need them to the relevant places in those subjects. I'm trying to get him to get help (P4).

There is no counseling teacher in our school. In other words, if they are small-scale psychological problems, we try to solve them by talking to the class counseling teacher or with the teachers with whom they get along well. There have been situations that have exceeded us before, such as having a little more nervous breakdown. Then we contact the counseling teacher closest to our school and talk to him immediately. We are trying to solve such a problem. (P2)

There is no coun teacher in our school. In addition; there are students whose parents are separated or divorced. A monitoring-counseling teacher is absolutely necessary for these children. Because we are not experts in these matters. Those kids don't tell you their problems. Those children's affective skills are impaired. It is necessary to take care of them. As a Subject counseling teacher, there are three students in my class. I try to help them through my counselor teacher friend outside of school. I dearly want UNESCO's "Education for All 2015 Inclusion" views to be implemented (P1)

Students who exhibited undesired behaviors at school, who experienced behavioral disorders, who had psychological problems / troubles were asked what the methods or solutions were, and the participants stated that they gave verbal / written warnings, applied methods such as advising, communicating with parents, trying to understand, and if the problem was large, they referred them to the Student Behavior Evaluation Board.

Of course, we have students with conduct disorders. Let's say fifth grades to eighth grades, especially among different age groups. When someone lives with the dream of graduating and leaving, they are in the mode of "we are the top students of the school, we own this place", but the fifth graders are in the mode of "we have just arrived, here we are still novices". Large classes can bully small classes. The student can distress his other friend in all kinds of ways, rich, poor, cultural, social, and economic (P5).

I have students who have behavior problems. We especially have children with hyperactivity problems. We have a lot of trouble fighting inside the school. Children in particular bully each other both verbally. Sometimes they bully as physical violence, and of course it is up to the teacher on duty or the teachers who attend his class to solve this incident. So it's up to us and we're trying to help with that. First of all, we warn children to make behavioral changes. Then

we say we will report it to the Student Behavior Review Board and give a definite warning. In other words, we make a definite warning about bullying, we keep a record. We are planning to activate the Student Behaviour Review Board again this year as we did last year (P4).

From time to time, such generations come with behavioral problems. Let me put it that way. When I first came to this school, the eighth graders were quite naughty. These "butcher children" were exactly what I call them, such as those who grew up among the tradesmen with the mouth of the tradesmen, who according to him behaved in such a way that they were older than their age, and there were children whom you could call disrespectful. It's a little bit more broken right now, but we still have students who are in our classrooms right now. So, for example, I'm not in eighth grade classes right now, but because of their behavior during recess, because my own students are in sixth grade or something, or because of their behavior outside of school, there are students who get used to come and go when they go out of school. There are especially spoiled boys in the eighth grade with conduct disorder. We have formed the disciplinary committee for the last year. In other words, when the complaints started to get a little more serious, we tried to calm down the behaviors of the student by forming the disciplinary board, giving the necessary warning to his family and withdrawing the student and explaining the punishments, the comments about his punishments, and what disadvantages these penalties would bring him for the future. This year, I see that the disciplinary board will work actively. When anything happens, I hope that we will try to solve the discipline problem immediately with the minutes when there is an above-normal behavior. (P2)

The participants, who were consulted about whether these applied solutions/suggestions worked, mentioned the measures taken and the temporariness of the solutions implemented. They mentioned that it worked a little better in the parents involved, but it was still far from being permanent:

It works temporarily because when it is permanent, we would not have a recurrence of this problem. Unfortunately, temporary solutions do not create temporary problems. It turns into a chronic one in the form of permanent problems (P5).

It works for our students whose families are a little bit interested, but in children whose parents are indifferent and who have a lot of behavioral disorders, of course what we say goes to waste after two days (P4).

Especially in those types of students, it's temporary. So it's like a moon effect. After his father's warning, he seems to pay attention to his behavior for a week and continue. You know, that year is over, the new year has begun. Of course, they're growing up, they're teenagers, they're eighth graders. So they see themselves as big. They became the elders of the school. Because of these, they can forget such a moment, so childhood, adolescence, we have all lived. But to remind you that a new disciplinary board may need a new report. Because, you know, we saw the yes effect last year, a summer passed when it was done, and they continued with the same behavior. They met with friends. A new report seems to have been forgotten at the moment because there is no new disciplinary board (P2).

We do parent-school-teacher cooperation. We try to give one-on-one attention and counseling to our students. In addition, the coaching system is being developed and implemented in our schools. Student, parent, school and teacher success-failure chain is better followed. The state gives textbooks, auxiliary resources. In addition, students who do not have the condition are helped by the Municipality and related ministries. These also support the parents and students to some extent (P1).

5. Permanent solutions to problems

In the fifth sub-problem of the opinions of teachers working in socio-economically disadvantaged secondary schools on permanent solutions to the problems they experienced are given below.

When the participants were asked what can be done permanently throughout the country or district/school on the basis of students or teachers to these problems experienced by teachers and their suggestions, it was mentioned that the suggestions that could be permanent were difficult, that there were temporary solutions, that there were things that could be done before the Ministry throughout the country for permanent solutions and other solution suggestions.

We need to come up with more serious solutions that we can do about these issues. For this, it is necessary to give training to students about anger management, to sign permanent contracts, to talk about the seriousness of minutes and formal documents, and to train students who use disproportionate force on this subject. We see that receiving warnings is not valid; it's temporary. Therefore, it may be to direct such students to the relevant places, to increase the cooperation between the student, parents and the school administration by making family visits and to establish more intimate relations. To give importance to family education and if necessary, to gather the parents of the students to certain conference halls available in schools or in the district from time to time and to give seminars. In other words, since we say that "education starts in the family", I think that we should first raise the awareness level of those at home and then make the students feel this to us. One of our permanent solutions to the problems we face is that training programs should be organized for parents as well as the education given by the Ministry of National Education to both students and teachers. This process can be managed by the Ministry of National Education. Of course, we can send the contents to homes in booklets or slides, or they can provide us with feedback. Then, the Ministry of National Education should definitely follow up on this. Just like the inspectors inspect us... After the trainings given about the parents, feedback can be taken again. Then we will see how useful the feedback is (P5).

As teachers, I think we should start from schools first, and then, for example, the region where we live, that is, from private to general. As I said, starting from the school and starting from the teachers in the school, towards our ministry in general, or our teachers can make decisions as a community or combine the problems and combine the solution methods and produce such a solution. There may be projects, for example, projects can be produced. There are also a lot of educational projects on this subject. At first, we can educate the parent, that is, the family, and then the children can be educated in different subjects. We can produce such solutions. However, it remains difficult to find a permanent solution (P4).

In my opinion, it is very difficult for the teacher to find a permanent solution for students who are sociologically disadvantaged in terms of school or district. What we can do is only listen to the problems of those who have these problems temporarily, and we can alleviate their distress by guiding them. Because we can't solve his family problem, we can't solve his economic problem. You know, we can take their books, we can give them their books, which we already do. You know, the permanent solution is only to equalize all the families in general if it is karsa from Edirne. So it's something that can happen with an economic click up. No. Teachers are only trying to save students who are badly affected by that economic disadvantage within the school, and these are always temporary solutions. It's just that we don't know what he was going through in high school when we sent him from here to high school. So there are no permanent solutions we can do. We can call it a permanent solution, but only the state is doing it again in terms of source books, and now it is sending workbooks and so on, but this is still not enough. Instead, students in such places can be identified name by name, determined according to their economic level and given gift certificates for all the source books they can use during the year. For example, rather than the workbook, I gave this book not to study, but to take whichever book he needs, whichever one the teacher recommends, with gift certificates. This may be the permanent solution of the source book, but as I said, the essence of the permanent solution starts from home. The house cannot be touched by the teacher's hand. This needs to be touched a little more within the state. It is the work of our elders (P2).

I foresee an increase in teachers' stationery allowances (P3).

I would also like to thank the Ministry of National Education for the 240-hour seminar on education and training that the Ministry of National Education has given us these days. Because education is a process and it is in a constant state of development. New problems (such as the pandemic) are emerging in the world. Teachers also have to renew themselves by virtue of the vision. I think that a teacher who knows and implements inclusive educational practices can be more productive. Teacher selections should be voluntary. EU teacher qualifications should be implemented. Schools need to establish emotion coaching centers. Children's social, affective skills need to be increased. In order to raise critical, self-confident, open-minded and technology-savvy students, inclusive educational environments should be increased and the "understanding of education for all" should be spread. In addition, counseling teachers should be taken to frequent seminars and academicians should be trained in this subject. Academics should also train teachers who can descend to the level of society (P1).

6. Findings regarding documents

Document analysis was carried out by using the documents of Kemalettin Sami Pasa Secondary School. By using the documents of 2022-2023 related to the subject, data were reached on the subject. The findings of this study as a result of the examination of the documents were aimed at understanding whether there was a basis for the problems and solutions experienced by the teachers. Kemalettin Sami Pasha Secondary School was a secondary school with 89 students, 1 principal and 1 assistant principal. There were no officers at the school. There was 1 employee and 13 teachers. Some of the teachers joined as assignments from other schools.

Problems Faced by Teachers, Reasons of Problems and Solutions/Suggestions They Produce

The number of documents examined in the document analysis conducted to understand the reasons of the problems faced by the teachers is presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2.

Number of Documents Examined in Document Analysis

Document Subject	Number of Documents Examined
1. Problems caused by students	416
a. Student Absenteeism	89
b. Student Conduct	170
c. Student Success	157
1. Problems Arising from Relations with Higher Authorities	134
a. Formal Meetings	34
b. Urgent Journals and Requests	100
Total	550

Problems caused by students

Table 3.

Student absenteeism

Class	Number of Students	Average Number of Absences
Grade 8	26	1,50
Grade 7	17	1,09
Grade 6	30	2,08
Grade 5	16	0,85
Total	89	5,52

Student absenteeism

When the documents of the 2022-2023 academic year were examined, it was understood that a foreign student did not come to school by constantly absent. In addition, the absenteeism rates obtained by examining the class documents and student report cards are given in Table 3.

In the 2022-2023 academic year, a total of 55 absence letters were prepared to the parents of the students. 1 of these letters belonged to the foreign student who was constantly absent and the sending process was not carried out, and the remaining 54 letters were sent to the parents of the students and informed.

Student behavior

When the documents for the 2022-2023 academic year were examined, a total of 4 students were referred to the Student Behavior Evaluation Board and were dismissed with reprimand punishment. In addition, a total of 5 students were warned both verbally and in writing by signing a contract on the condition that they would not repeat the behavior due to the undesired behaviors they exhibited.

Student success

When the year-end records of the 2022-2023 academic year were examined, it was understood that 24 students were entitled to receive the certificate of excellence and 28 students were entitled to receive the certificate of appreciation. 34 of the students had at least one low mark. Student achievement status are presented as follows.

Table 4.

Student success

Class	Number of students per class	Number of students receiving excellence	Number of students receiving appreciation	Number of students who had at least one low mark	Unsuccessful students total students to rate
Grade 8	26	8	8	8	%30
Grade 7	17	2	6	9	%52
Grade 6	30	11	7	11	%36
Grade 5	16	3	7	6	%37,5
Total	89	24	28	34	%38,2

Problems arising from relations with higher authorities

Formal meetings

When the school's documents for 2022-2023 were examined, teachers attended in-service training meetings after hours on average 3 times a year. In addition, they were invited to the Teachers' Board Meeting held at the school 3 times a year, to the Subject Teachers' Board Meeting 3 times a year, to the Group Teachers Board Meeting 3 times a year, to the Student Behavior Evaluation Board meeting 1 time during the year, and to the parents' meetings 3 times a year.

Urgent daily letters and requests

When the documents coming to and leaving the school in the 2022-2023 academic year were examined, approximately 30% of the documents were urgent and expected to be signed by the teachers and the participation was requested, and the remaining 70% are the documents that were expected to be answered daily. In addition, student achievement status and coaching progress certificates requested from teachers are also a factor that tired teachers during the year. The disadvantage of the region and the school also

made it very difficult for teachers to present realistic results to higher authorities.

Conclusion and Discussion

In this study, teachers' views on the problems they faced and experienced in socio-economically disadvantaged regional secondary schools were investigated qualitatively. In this section, the findings obtained as a result of the research and the results of analyzes are included.

As a result of the research, it was revealed that teachers had many problems in school and in working life, there was a general consensus about the main reasons of the problems, the discomforts were common, the problems wore the teachers down a lot, but despite all this, it was understood that the teachers tried to do their best, applied temporary methods / solutions and performed their duties appropriately.

In the research, the importance of counseling services was understood and it was seen what kind of problems teachers dealt with in case of deficiency. This study revealed the difficulty of teachers to reach big goals with children who struggled with family problems, who experienced the negative effects of the environment, who had small dreams, and the extent to which the effects of the environment they lived in were, and how family, economic, social and cultural problems forced students and teachers. Distractions, undesired student behaviors, not being prepared for the lesson, indifference of parents, students not feeling valuable, low literacy rate in the environment and family and lack of people who would set an example for students, unplanned work of students, lack of access to source books, lack of social activities, fragmented family structures and dilemma between parents of students, problems of adaptation of foreign students to school and region, and situations such as cultural problems were mentioned as factors that affected both students and teachers. In a similar study, Lupton (2003) investigated the effect of conditions, namely general situation, on school process and quality in disadvantaged regional secondary schools, and investigated the effect of socio-economic status on school success in disadvantaged regions by comparing them with central schools. By mentioning the existence of low quality and giving place to the success results of the previous years, he concluded that the achievements in rural or disadvantaged places were low. In addition, Taşdemir (2016) examined the problems faced by social studies teachers working in socially disadvantaged areas, in his study, the difficulty of accessing the source books due to the low socio-economic status of the students, the overcrowded classrooms due to inadequacy, the pushing of education to the second place due to economic conditions, the indifferent attitudes of the students to the lesson. On the other hand, it was concluded that teachers were not satisfied with their status and salary, had difficulties in accessing course materials, and insufficient course hours. In Önal's (2020) study, which dealt with the problems faced by teachers working in socio-economically disadvantaged preschool institutions during the implementation of science activities, it was also stated that teachers were exposed to an event or problem in terms of disadvantage at least once, and the socio-economic situation of the family was the reason for these. Reasons such as low level of education, unconscious behavior of families, low literacy rate, low family participation, ethnic differences were found as a result. In summary, in such socio-economically disadvantaged regions, these problems, which affect not only students or their families but also all teachers, appear as an ongoing chain of problems and stories and situations that will be the subject of sociologists' researches occur.

In the document analysis conducted by the researcher, a total of 550 documents were examined. 416 of these documents were related to the problems of teachers arising from students. When these documents were examined, absenteeism rates, negative student behaviors, student failures were at a level that would enable the teacher to face many problems. Due to the high absenteeism rates, the parent and the school were responsible as well as the student for the child's attendance at school. When the absenteeism rates were examined, it was concluded that it was not low not only in the upper grades but also in other grades except for the 5th grade, and this was one of the problems that teachers were dealing with. With these absences, students fell behind in their lessons, did not participate in the lesson, did not even take the

exams and the teacher dealt with the student. With the absence letters sent, the necessary warnings were made to the parents in this regard.

In addition, apart from the documents examined, the preparation of a report for a total of 10 students due to their undesirable behavior was evidence of how much they forced the teacher and caused problems. In a study on undesired student behaviours, Elban (2009), in his study titled Examination of the situations of facing undesirable student behaviors and finding solutions by the teachers working at the primary education level, he states that the students are indifferent to the lesson, complaining about their friends, the student walking around the classroom without permission, excessive and unauthorized speaking behaviors, and to deal with those behaviours, teachers use activities that will attract the attention of the students.. He also states that teachers use methods such as dealing with the student one-on-one, getting support from the school administration and counseling service, showing the right behavior, giving responsibility to the student, disregarding, verbal warning, punishment and reward.

When the success and failure status table was examined, the failure rate of a student who was weak in at least one course is 38.2% on average. Considering this situation, if the school success was low, both parents, senior management, school administration and the environment would put pressure on teachers. It was also a known fact that always in the eyes of the society and senior management, if there was success, the student had done it; if there was failure, the teacher was to blame, he did not do his job well.

In the second part, a total of 134 documents were examined in order to reveal the problems arising from the relations with the higher authorities, and 70% of these documents consisted of daily writings, and the very urgent writings that teachers had to sign and participate in were 30% of these documents. According to the conclusion to be drawn from this, the urgent writings requested in the institution caused problems that would affect the private life of the teacher and force the teacher to work out-of-hours. In addition, the fact that teachers were called to meetings or held meetings about 16-20 times a year on average adds a new one to the workload of teachers in the school and caused them to disrupt their lessons and worked in school and is a problem.

Recommendations

In consistent with the results obtained, following suggestions can be put forward:

As a result of this study, which was conducted in order to identify the problems faced by teachers working in socio-economically disadvantaged regional secondary schools and to understand and interpret the solutions they applied for the problems they experienced, some of the following suggestions can be presented:

Through parent visits, a stronger communication link should be established between the school, the family and the student.

The reasons of the problems faced with referrals to the counseling service should be investigated and in serious cases, situations should be communicated to the relevant institutions.

At the beginning of the problems, the student should be discussed, the source of the problem should be questioned and ignoring / depriving the reward, written, verbal warning and warning methods should be applied.

The implementation and dissemination of the inclusive education approach should be carried out by the ministry.

In order to strengthen the school-family cooperation, school-parent association meetings should be held more frequently, in accordance with their purpose, and in a way that increases the participation of parents in school administration.

The Student Behavior Evaluation Board should be made more active and the seriousness of the minutes kept to the students and the steps to be taken in case of undesirable behavior should be explained at the beginning of the year and a serious stance should be taken on this issue.

The quality of student coaching services should be increased and their function should be increased by making it a duty of responsibility to the teacher willingly, not as a chore.

Necessary steps to increase the social and cognitive skills of students should be taken both at the ministry and at the provincial centers.

In-service trainings that exist for teachers to renew themselves should not be carried out outside of working hours.

By increasing the quality and counseling services, the need for counseling teachers in every school should be eliminated and counseling teachers should be provided.

Students should be trained on anger management and presentations, visuals and videos about counseling should be used.

The family trainings, seminars and conferences that are currently being given should be made more functional, parents should be encouraged to participate in these trainings voluntarily rather than forcibly, the purpose should be explained in a clear language and these trainings should be given by experts from the Ministry of Family and Social Policies or the Ministry of National Education, not teachers.

The efforts to increase the equality of opportunity and opportunity in education throughout the country should be further increased and developed by using the school allowances that started to be given this year efficiently and correctly. The grants should be followed up and necessary steps should be taken to use them for the benefit of the teacher and the student.

Incentives for teachers working in disadvantaged regions in terms of points or wages should be increased and the productivity of employees should be supported to do their jobs for solutions in these regions away from financial concerns.

Especially considering the problems faced by teachers working in disadvantaged areas, the reputation of teachers should be increased throughout the country and the safety of teachers should be ensured in order to minimize and eliminate incidents of violence against teachers.

Considering that teachers face so many problems, social activities should be increased more and student-teacher-parent should be integrated and problems should be reduced.

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Ethical approval

In the writing process of the study titled “**Problems faced by teachers working in secondary schools in socio-economic disadvantaged regions and suggestions for solutions: A case study**”, the rules of scientific, ethical and citation were followed; it was undertaken by the authors of this study that no falsification was made on the collected data, “Journal Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research [JAQMER] and Editor” had no responsibility for all ethical violations to be faced, and all responsibility belongs to the authors and that the study was not submitted for evaluation to any other academic publishing environment.

Ethics committee approval

Ethics Committee Approval of this research was obtained from Akdeniz University Social Sciences Ethics Committee at the meeting of 01 decision numbered 08 on January 10th, 2023.